

SHORT NOTES

Anion-exchange Studies on the Separation of Uranium and Rare Earths

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The existence of nitrate and chloride complexes of uranium is well known and this property has been made use of for its separation from iron, aluminium, and vanadium by anion-exchange method^{1,2}. Separation of rare earths from uranium was studied earlier by Dolar and Draganic³, using a cation-exchanger, and Susic⁴ by anion-exchanger in dilute sulphuric acid. In a previous communication⁵ from this laboratory, separation of uranium from thorium in 6*N*-HCl medium by anion-exchange was reported. The present note deals with the extension of the same method to the separation of uranium from rare earths. The resin, Amberlite IRA-400, of mesh size 30-40 was used in the present study.

Procedure.—Resin (10 g.) was taken in a glass column of 8" tall and 0.5" diameter. The column was preconditioned by passing 200 ml of the acid of required strength. Rare earths used in all the experiments had the following composition:

To ascertain the extent of adsorption under the experimental conditions, solutions of the mixed earths in 4-7*N* HCl were run through the column and practically no adsorption was found. Solutions of synthetic mixtures containing different amounts and proportions of U_3O_8 and R_2O_3 in 200 ml of 6*N*-HCl were run separately through the column at the rate of 3 ml/min. The column was then washed with about 100 ml of 6*N*-HCl. In each case, the effluent was found to be free from uranium and the rare earths were precipitated as hydroxides and estimated as oxides. The uranium adsorbed on the resin was then eluted with 0.5*N*-HCl, precipitated with ammonia, and estimated as U_3O_8 . The uranium oxide thus obtained was found to be free from rare earths in the range of U_3O_8 to R_2O_3 ratios of 1:1 to 1:1000.

The efficiency of this method of separation was further tested by using a crude sample of sodium diuranate containing 0.6457% Th, 1.707% R.E.^s and 0.4349% Fe as major impurities (on U_3O_8 basis). The sample (250 g.) was dissolved in about 2000 ml of 6*N*-HCl and passed through a column containing one pound resin. The column was then washed

1. Oekenden and Foreman, *Analyst*, 1957, **82**, 592.
2. Morachevski and Gordeeva, *Anal. Abst.*, 1958, **5**, 1195.
3. *Chem. Abs.*, 1953, **47**, 6816.
4. *Anal. Abst.*, 1958, **5**, 829.
5. Kunte and Sen, *Curr. Sci.*, 1958, **27**, 94.

with about 500 ml of 6*N*-HCl. The anions adsorbed in the column were eluted with 0.5*N*-HCl and the solution analysed. The results in Table I record the extent of removal of the impurities from the initial uranyl solution.

TABLE I

Impurity.	% Present initially.	% Present after ion-exchange treatment.	% Removal of the impurity.
Thorium	0.0457	0.0165	97.43
Rare earths	1.7070	0.0063	99.61
Iron	0.4349	0.3750	13.77

These results show that uranium can be separated from thorium and rare earths by this method, but the removal of iron is not satisfactory.

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Received October 19, 1962.